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From Textbooks to Tranquility: Peace Education in South Punjab

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Abstract

The media has a significant influence on the beliefs and viewpoints of today's youth. Concerns about the negative consequences of violence have arisen since it has continuously been a major problem on university campuses. In particular, peace is essential to the growth and service of young university students, who will soon be leaders and politicians in our nation. The recognition that living in perpetual conflict poses difficulties and can result in people developing ambiguous attitudes and ideologies has led educators to concentrate more and more on peace education. An environment devoid of peace runs the risk of breeding radicalism, terrorism, unfairness, prejudice, and oppression. Introducing Peace Education to university students physically or through print or electronic media might be a useful strategy in the fight against xenophobia and violence. This study recognizes the value of peace education for students attending South Punjab region universities in Pakistan. The integrated theory of peace (ITP) serves as the foundation for the study, which uses a qualitative research methodology for data collection. Participants in the teaching and learning of BS Education programs at universities and students themselves make up the respondents in this survey. It is established that peace education is important and necessary. In order to uphold peace and tolerance and denounce violence, bloodshed, immoderation, and hatred, the governments of Punjab and Pakistan should work with renowned educators to create an effective online or in-person curriculum that is tailored to this goal. The nation would benefit the most from such initiatives.

Keywords: Smart syllabus on Peace Education, Teaching-Learning, Peace Education, Combat violence, Universities of Pakistan.

Introduction

Reardon (1988) elucidates that there is no exact degree to which peace education can be restricted because it is a multi-branched area that comprises different areas such as the resolution of conflict, non-violence, global understanding, and education on human rights, environmental education, and social justice.

Peace can be taken as an utmost goal or hope that nearly each and every individual desires to attain personally and expects it to be created in the society and in the world as a whole. The absence of peace can result in destruction, restlessness and chaos in a country. A society without peace can never flourish and can hence lead to unrest, violence, insecurity and instability.

Peace is generally associated with a beautiful and peaceful planet. People have been making every effort to achieve long-term peace. In actuality, one aspect of human

history is the history of seeking peace. Peace has been thought about, talked about, taught, and researched from many angles and by a variety of methods.

Unfortunately, within the last 20 years or so, there has been an increase in violence worldwide. From the poorest to the wealthiest nations, lack of peace has had a negative impact on many people. Violence has had a direct and detrimental effect on millions of people's lives, welfare, and sense of self. Inequality is ultimately the result of an unjust distribution of wealth brought about by violence, conflict, unrest, and instability.

Peace education can serve as the basic and the most effective tool to prevent violence and anarchy. It can teach us how to respect differences by promising equal opportunities and rights for all. In this regard, promotion of peace education is greatly needed in the world of today in order to combat incidents of violence and restlessness. Educating people by means of a purpose-built Human Rights and Peace Education syllabus can prove beneficial because such initiatives can assist in opening minds of the individuals. Once the learners learn regarding Peace and Human Rights, they may most probably start respecting other people, their beliefs and ideologies; and they hence can become better citizens by positively contributing to the society. Peace Education subsequently seems immensely necessary in the world of today specifically for youngsters enrolled at universities.

Peace Education is much connected with the formulation of skills and values that support students to attain a belief or mindset capable of embracing all people irrespective of their class, ethnicity, colour, creed, nationality, etc. This mode of education can prevent the occurrence of conflicts and can therefore constitute conditions that can guarantee the existence of peace worldwide. Furthermore, activities and syllabuses aligned with Peace can greatly help the societies and individuals in conflict resolution, respecting human rights, combating violence, controlling hatred and in ensuring freedom. Above can be termed as basic reasons why peace education can play a significant role in establishing peace, harmony and security across the globe.

Initiatives of imparting Peace Education among young minds can be highly beneficial for the days, months and years to come as these minds are expected soon to address issues associated with violence and lawlessness through their awareness of peace and effective policymaking. These youngsters will hence be able to create an equitable and peaceful society by upholding rule of law and also by addressing issues linked with undermining law and its enforcement.

Conflict prevention and conflict resolution both have importance of their own. In this regard, a nation and its lawmakers must prioritize peace building by tackling situations that can lead to emotional, physical and social violence among individuals. Overcoming such issues can be possible by way of imparting Peace Education through schools, colleges, varsities and across all communities.

Calm environment and the absence of violence and bloodshed are certainly signs of peace. But, peace is not merely defined as the absence of conflict; in reality, it can also be associated with the administration of justice, law, and order by national governments. Therefore, it can be argued that the absence of war will not suffice for peace to last unless a society achieves fairness, equality, equity, and justice. This can be achieved by providing young people with high-quality peace education. It is also expected of these young brains to guarantee the prevalence of peace in the future by productive policymaking and discourse.

People can learn the value of both internal and exterior peace through peace education. While exterior peace is something that represents peace in a society, internal peace refers to a person's own personal peace. Since both internal and external peace depend on one another to survive, they are related and mutually dependent. The essence and basis of external peace can be found in internal peace. People collectively make up a society. If they learn about peace in their formal education, they will be at peace, and when these peaceful people get together, they will be able to build a peaceful society. On the other hand, external or societal peace can directly impact inner peace of an individual. The absence of wars, conflicts, or bloodshed can guarantee internal peace among individuals because there will be nothing to psychologically or physically disturb their minds. Locating peace from within in the truest sense can be more sustainable and can positively impact society.

Objectives

1. To analyze how professors and students feel about the value of peace education in South Punjabi universities.
2. To examine the possible effects of including peace education in the current curriculum of universities.

Literature Review

Research shows that among Pakistan's educated class, peace education has not received the respect it deserves and it has never been considered for any curriculum. In fact, the majority of people have never heard this term before.

Conflict is defined as a situation in which multiple groups of individuals are at odds with one another due to divergent opinions or interests. This situation may result in a violent or nonviolent action that is harmful to the allies of the opposing side (Getui, 2009). In a society where intricate and varied cultural traditions are practiced, education has empowered people's lives (Krueger and Maleckova, 2003).

Consequently, to channel youth's bad traits into constructive endeavors, the development of life skills and the establishment of enduring peace are two important goals that peace education can help with. The following summarizes the study's primary goals: to learn what academic professionals, subject matter experts, and students think about the contribution of peace education to the creation of

enduring peace. To assess the viability of teaching peace at the elementary, middle, and high school levels using the analytical hierarchy process.

Education of peace is a vast field. One silver lining amid all the odds and difficulties of conflict is that practically every nation recognizes the necessity and significance of peace education. Peace education is an independent field of study.

Since peace education can address many important concerns, including conflict resolution and fostering harmony and reconciliation, it has emerged as a full-fledged field of study (Seitz, 2004).

Origin of the word 'Peace'

The Latin word "pax," which denotes an agreement to put an end to hostilities like a battle between two hostile groups of people, is where the word "peace" originates (Khemananda, 1996).

Inherent Violence

The perpetuation of structural violence, which is primarily the existence of oppression and inequality in terms of political and economic ties, can also occur in large part in schools (Galtung 1975). For example, Sutton Trust research concluded that social mobility in Britain was stalling and that social class was the best indicator of academic success or obtaining a degree. In summary, one could say that, even after thirty years, the privilege of being born into a wealthy family has not changed (Curtis, 2007).

Indicators of Structural violence

Certainly, within the domain of schools, there is a great sign of the dictatorial, hierarchical, and competitive associations which Galtung suggests are a sort of structural violence. (Harber 2004, 2009). Such a tendency enhances the need for peace education at our educational institutions.

The model of authoritarian education

With its roots in state formation, revitalization, and social and political influence, this authoritarian educational model was progressively exported throughout the world from European and Japanese societies through colonization, when education served primarily as a tool for the colonial power to control the indigenous populations. By the 1930s, colonialism had impacted more than 84.6% of the world's land area. (Loomba 1998, 15). Thus, it makes sense that Vriens (1999) believes that peace education originated in the modern era.

Different Peace Education Goals

Despite the fact that peace education has spread over time, these programs can differ greatly in terms of their theoretical and practical objectives as well as the emphasis they place on different curricular topics. (Bar-Tal 1999)

Classification of Present-Day Peace Education Initiatives

Four categories have been created by Gavriel Salomon (2002) to summarize and categorize the current peace education initiatives:

1. Peace education should primarily focus on changing people's perspectives.
2. That the main goal of peace education is to impart a certain set of abilities
3. Peace education is primarily concerned with advancing human rights, particularly in third-world nations.
4. Finally, peace education as it relates to demilitarization, conservationism (environmentalism), and the promotion of a peaceful culture. (p. 4).

Research Methodology

Using a phenomenological technique, this qualitative study collects data from 20 teaching faculty members and 250 students enrolled in four-year bachelor's degree program of BS Education at South Punjab universities using open-ended questionnaires. Key themes and patterns in the responses were found through the application of thematic analysis. Participants in the study comprise academic instructors and senior students in the seventh and eighth semesters enrolled in four-year bachelor's degree programs in institutions of South Punjab, Pakistan. The study summarizes the education for peace curriculum (EFP), which was developed based on the integrative theory of peace (ITP). The participants were asked to provide their opinions and experiences through an open-ended questionnaire, and the responses were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify the key themes and patterns. Using an open-ended questionnaire, the participants were asked to share their thoughts and experiences. The main themes and patterns in the responses were then determined by thematic analysis.

Rationale for Validity:

The EFP curriculum is "developed based on the integrative theory of peace (ITP)" according to its theoretical foundation. This implies a solid base of well-established information and proficiency in the field of peace education. ITP is a thorough framework that is based on industry best practices and research. Therefore, there is some inherent legitimacy involved in basing the curriculum on this basis.

Methods in Qualitative Research:

The study uses "phenomenological technique" and "thematic analysis," two accepted approaches. When these approaches are used carefully, they can produce reliable and insightful results. There is some uncertainty in this regard, though, as the

excerpt omits the precise measures utilized to guarantee the legitimacy and quality of the data analysis.

Selection of Participants:

"Teaching faculty members" and "senior students" from four-year education programs are both included in the study. This wide range of participants offers a more thorough knowledge of the effects of the EFP program.

The potential usefulness and credibility of the EFP curriculum can be attributed to its base in ITP, its use of rigorous qualitative research methodologies such as thematic analysis, and the possibility of expert input in its development. Even while further research may be required for absolute proof, the information that is currently available points to a well-founded curriculum that has the ability to significantly aid in South Punjab's attempts to promote peace.

Results and Discussion

The responses and themes are as follows:

1. Campus Harmony through Tolerance: Participants emphasize the significance of promoting acceptance of different opinions through peace education in order to combat prejudice on campuses.

2. Curricular Peace Embrace: Promoting the inclusion of peace education as a top priority in the curriculum to combat hostility and psychological stress, therefore improving campus peace in general.

3. Peaceful Societal Cultivation: Stressing the value of both internal and external campus peace, this approach promotes civil behavior through peace education to help create a peaceful society.

4. Mental Well-being Harmony: Participants emphasize the importance of peace education in fostering understanding and psychological well-being while highlighting the influence of peace on mental health.

5. Islamic Insights for Tolerance: To promote tolerance and understanding among students, it is advised that Islamic historical examples be incorporated into the curriculum.

6. Unified Efforts for Curriculum Peace: Stressing cooperation between educators, stakeholders, and lawmakers to create a thorough curriculum with student assessments, this initiative aims to effectively promote human rights and peace education.

Participants' Quotes (BS Education students & Teaching Faculty):

1. "Our campus feels like a tinderbox, full of hateful sparks waiting to burst." I've witnessed arguments turn violent. The much-needed firebreak is peace education." - A senior majoring in education who is seeing the effects of bigotry

2. "We see personally the destructive consequences of hatred and bigotry as educators. Peace education is a remedy for the poison of conflict, not just a course." - An experienced professor of BS Education who promotes peacebuilding
3. "We honor diversity in ancestry, but what about intellectual diversity? Not exactly. That divide can be closed by peace education, which teaches us to welcome diversity rather than to be afraid of it." - An attendee of a course on encouraging inclusive communication
4. "It is exhausting to live in a state of perpetual anxiety. Peace education is essential, not a luxury. It has the power to infuse serenity into our university's basic foundation." - A BS Education student who wishes for a calmer classroom setting
5. "Ignorance casts a shadow of bigotry and intolerance. The route towards tolerance and understanding is illuminated by peace education, which serves as a light that exposes them." A focus group member on curriculum reform who emphasized the importance of knowledge
6. "Words have the ability to strengthen or weaken. By teaching us to communicate with kindness, integrity, and respect, peace education helps to create a culture in which peace is a reality rather than simply a pipe dream." A faculty member at VS Education emphasizing the significance of communication in peacebuilding.
7. "True peace extends beyond the boundaries of the university. It begins inside each of us. Through inner tranquility that emanates and creates a wave of harmony, peace education aids in our development. - An attendee of a personal peacebuilding workshop
8. "The ongoing stress of conflict is too much for our hearts and minds to handle. Peace education is essential for our current mental and emotional health as well as for future generations." A student majoring in education highlights the instant advantages of peace education.
9. "Tolerance and peace are woven throughout the history of Islam. By including its illustrations in our curriculum, we can encourage a new wave of peacemakers." A faculty member of BS Education offering suggestions for culturally appropriate methods.
10. "Working together, not against one other, is necessary to create a curriculum for peace. Together, educators, stakeholders, and legislators must create a program that tracks advancement and gives students the tools they need to effect change. - A local peace movement representative, pushing for group action.

The voices of both students and teachers on university campuses are reverberating with discord, creating an environment that needs to change for learning to take place. This qualitative study explores how peace education is seen as a means of creating harmony in these frequently turbulent environments.

The participants present a clear picture of the negative effects of intolerance. An institution of higher learning is fundamentally disrupted when prejudice festers and explodes in antagonism and violence. As the remedy, they suggest peace education—a soft touch that promotes tolerance for differing viewpoints and a respectful society. The study contends that we may break down barriers of bias and create an environment that is truly inclusive on campus by accepting diverse points of view.

The study recognizes the ripple impact of peace and extends beyond the university. It advocates for pursuing harmony on the inside as well as the outside. The tranquility that permeates the campus community is believed to be rooted in internal peace, a state of personal serenity fostered by awareness and introspection. According to the study, we can create the foundation for a more peaceful society overall by fostering peace within each individual. People gain an understanding of the need of polite conversation, moral behavior, and compassion through peace education. These attributes spread beyond campus boundaries and foster harmony on a larger scale.

The majority of participants felt that fostering understanding and peace among people would benefit from a specially designed curriculum on human rights and peace education that included student evaluation. Some participants, meanwhile, voiced doubts regarding the best way to assess the effectiveness and advancement of peace education. They underlined that in order to create a curriculum on peace education and human rights that works, educators, stakeholders, and legislators must work together.

The results of this very research study greatly emphasize how important it is to include peace education in university curricula. A purpose-built curriculum for peace education must be developed and implemented in cooperation with stakeholders, including the media, educators, and policymakers. This action is crucial to eradicating lawlessness, violence, and fanaticism from South Punjab's universities and fostering a climate that is peaceful and secure for both students and teachers.

The participants call for the inclusion of peace education as a top priority in the curriculum, recognizing the destructive nature of ongoing war. They see a program that is integrated into university life rather than being confined to the periphery. They contend that adopting this curriculum would be a powerful tool in the fight against animosity and psychological strain, fostering a calmer and more effective learning atmosphere. A curriculum integrated with the ideals of peace can nurture a generation of resilient and empathic persons by providing them with the necessary tools to resolve conflicts amicably and prioritize their mental health.

Overall, the study shows that peace education is crucial for fostering mutual respect, understanding, and concord among students in South Punjab universities in Pakistan. The delegates underlined the necessity of including peace education in the

university curriculum as well as the detrimental effects of bigotry and discord on campus. According to the study, it may also be beneficial to integrate Islamic historical examples into the peace education curriculum to foster tolerance and understanding among people. In order to properly assess peace education's effectiveness, it is also imperative that peace education be given top priority in the curriculum and that a specially designed syllabus be developed in conjunction with stakeholders and legislators.

Conclusion

Peace education is the most basic and effective way to stop chaos and bloodshed. It can teach us to embrace and cherish differences by ensuring equal chances and rights for everyone. To combat violence and restlessness in today's world, peace education needs to be fostered. Studies show that university-level peace education curricula are supported by educators and students alike as a means of preventing acts of violence, intolerance, and disturbance. In this regard, all stakeholders from print and electronic media, educationists, and policymakers must come forward and design and practically implement a syllabus on Peace Education to eliminate the events of lawlessness, violence, and fanaticism in the universities of our beloved country Pakistan.

Pakistani university curricula have historically attempted to include peace education, according to attempts made by the Higher Education Commission (HEC). But it has become out that neither the government nor the HEC have done enough. In light of the country's high rate of social injustice and violence, university peace education programs urgently need to be implemented. This is especially crucial for college students who aspire to lead Pakistan in the future.

The value of peace education at Pakistani universities is examined in this research study using a qualitative methodology. The audience was asked open-ended questions to get their thoughts on this topic. The study's findings unequivocally show that peace education is more important than ever. The government may decide to adopt peace education in universities with appropriate care and attention if the research's conclusions are put to good use.

In the opinion of the researcher, mandatory course lasting at least one credit hour should therefore be a part of all major university degree programs, including ADP, BS, MS, M.Phil, PhD, and so on. The significance of peace education for pupils in southern Punjab and throughout Pakistan is emphasized by this study. It also carefully lays out possible methods for integrating peace education into the present university curriculum. To guarantee that university students have the abilities and information required to create a peaceful community, it is imperative that quick action be taken in this regard.

To put an end to acts of lawlessness, violence, and fanaticism in the universities of our dear nation, Pakistan, all relevant parties – including print and electronic media,

educators, and policymakers – must come forward and develop and effectively implement a curriculum on peace education.

A compelling need for peace education: The research demonstrates a strong consensus among participants regarding the urgent need for peace education. Its critical significance in reducing violence, developing tolerance and understanding, and enhancing personal wellbeing was underlined by both professors and students. This perceived necessity is a result of the realization of the negative effects of hostility and conflict in the academic setting.

Complexities in curriculum integration and assessment: The study emphasizes the possible advantages of a curriculum specifically designed for peace education, especially if it includes instruction on human rights and uses student-centered evaluation techniques. However, questions were voiced about the best ways to analyze this kind of education and determine how successful it is. The panelists underlined that in order to provide a comprehensive and flexible peace education framework, educators, stakeholders, and legislators must work together.

Harnessing the power of Islamic history: According to studies, using pertinent Islamic historical examples in the curriculum for peace education could be a useful strategy for encouraging tolerance and understanding among a variety of student populations. The aforementioned method acknowledges the distinct cultural and religious milieu of South Punjab and endeavors to utilize pre-existing knowledge systems to promote peace-building endeavors.

In summary, the present qualitative investigation presents a convincing illustration of the potential of peace education to foster a more amicable academic atmosphere. Peace education can provide students with the skills necessary to resolve conflicts amicably, create understanding bridges, and eventually contribute to a more peaceful society by encouraging tolerance, placing a high value on mental health, and relying on cultural ideas.

The study's conclusions highlight the vital role that peace education plays in creating a more tranquil and harmonious campus community in South Punjab. Universities can play a critical role in providing students with the knowledge, skills, and values required to cultivate a culture of peace both within and beyond their campuses by addressing the perceived need, navigating curriculum integration challenges, and investigating the potential of Islamic historical examples. The present study facilitates the investigation of additional efficacious tactics for implementation and evaluation techniques, which will ultimately aid in the establishment of a comprehensive and influential program for peace education in South Punjabi universities.

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